

Streaked Dwarf Porcupine (*Coendou ichillus*) in the Iquitos area (northeastern Peru)

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Summary

On the nights of 20 and 23 June 2023 I photographed Streaked Dwarf Porcupine (*Coendou ichillus*, Voss and da Silva, 2001) in lowland forest 60 km south of Iquitos (Loreto, northeastern Peru), having found both with a thermal scope whilst in the company of Juan Pacaya (a guide from Tahuayo Lodge). These two records appear to be the first in situ records from northeastern Peru. *C. ichillus* is a poorly known porcupine confirmed from only nine sites (Ramírez-Chaves et al, 2020). One of the two sites in Peru is the Iquitos area in northeastern Peru where the only known specimen is a juvenile purchased by Pekka Soini in 1971 from a market near Iquitos and its collection point was never known (Voss and da Silva, 2001).

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1. Site Data

These records are 60 km south of Iquitos and 2.4 km WSW of Chino, a small village on the Tahuayo River, a tributary of the Amazon River. The site is on the southern side of the Amazon River and within the Yavarí-Ucayali interfluvium described by Voss and Fleck (2011). They were seen on a trail from Tahuayo Lodge. Site data for the two records, referred to here as P1 and P2, are:

P1: S4.30956° W73.23964°. Elevation: 103 m. 900 m west of Tahuayo Lodge; 20 June 2023 at 9.52 PM; waypoint 861. Images are posted on iNat [here](#).

P2: S4.30976° W73.23715°. Elevation: 100 m. 270 m east of P1; 23 June 2023 at 10.23 PM; waypoint 937. Images are posted on iNat [here](#).

These sightings were in primary lowland forest that is subjected to seasonal flooding. This particular area was reportedly flooded until a month before the sightings.

C. ichillus remains poorly known in South America with records from only nine sites in Colombia, Ecuador, Peru and Brazil as summarised by Ramírez-Chaves et al (2020; Table 1). One of the two sites in Peru is the Iquitos area in northeastern Peru where the only known specimen is a juvenile purchased by Pekka Soini in 1971 from a market near Iquitos and its collection point was never known (Voss and da Silva, 2001). All records of *C. ichillus* are from elevations between 100 and 980 m (Ramírez-Chaves et al, 2020). The P1 and P2 sightings are on the south-eastern limit of the distribution maps shown in Weksler et al (2016; Red List data) and iNaturalist (2023 June); the most southern point of that distribution shown as 90 km south of Iquitos. However, Ramírez-Chaves et al (2020 Fig 2) show an updated range map that extends 900 km south of Iquitos to include the Cusco area records of Gregory et al (2015), the only other site in Peru. iNaturalist (2023 June) shows only three records (unconfirmed), the nearest being a sighting in Brazil by Almeida (2019) that is approximately 400 km south of Iquitos.

Fig 1: Location of Streaked Dwarf Porcupine observed 60 km south of Iquitos (at w-0861) in June 2023. Data plotted on Google Earth base map.

2. Species Identification

C. ichillus was described by Voss and da Silva (2001) as one of four species of the *Coendou vestitus* group, a group of *Coendou* that have bristle quills. Voss and da Silva (2001, see Fig 1) describe bristle quills as "much longer and thinner than conventional quills, but have the same distinctive root morphology" and the "tips of bristle-quills are attenuated, flexible, wire-like filaments, and they are not provided with microscopic barbs"; they are "long, thin, unbarbed quills with flexible tips". They describe *C. ichillus* as a "member of the *C. vestitus* group distinguished from other species by its long tail, lack of visible fur in the adult pelage, more extensively black-tipped quills, tricolored (pale-tipped) bristle-quills, spiny ventral pelage, and a unique combination of cranial traits" and where "the pale tips of the bristle-quills produce a characteristically streaked effect over the whole dorsum with the exception of the rump (which is covered only with short bicolored quills and a few wool hairs)". *C. ichillus* is known as Streaked Dwarf Porcupine in iNaturalist (2023 June) and Western Amazonian Dwarf Porcupine in Mammal Diversity Database (v-1.10).

The images of P1 (Figs 2a-c) show that it has bristle quills on the dorsum and mostly black-tipped yellow quills (bicoloured) and seemingly without three-banded (tricoloured) quills on the flanks. The images of P2 (Figs 3a-b) show an extensive amount of bristle quills (on the dorsal areas and flanks). The images of P1 are primarily of the right side of the body whereas P2 was photographed on its left side so it was not possible to determine from morphological features whether they were the same individual or not.

Long-tailed Porcupine (*Coendou longicaudatus*), the only other species known in this area, was split from *Coendou prehensilis*, the latter now endemic to Brazil (Menezes et al, 2021). They do not have bristle quills. I photographed three individuals on 20 June with one shown (Figs 4a-c) for quill comparison; these

images show quills on the flanks that are black-banded white quills (tricoloured / three banded) and show the lack of bristle quills.

Figs 2a-c: Streaked Dwarf Porcupine (*Coendou ichillus*) - Individual P1 (image # 20230620-0166)

Fig 2a: Streaked Dwarf Porcupine (*Coendou ichillus*): full body.

Fig 2b: Streaked Dwarf Porcupine (*Coendou ichillus*): bristle quills along the spine.

Fig 2c: Streaked Dwarf Porcupine (*Coendou ichillus*): spines on the flanks are mostly black-tipped and bicoloured; bristle quills are also present.

Figs 3a-b: Streaked Dwarf Porcupine (*Coendou ichillus*) – Individual P2 (image # 20230623-0320).

Fig 3a: Streaked Dwarf Porcupine (*Coendou ichillus*): full body.

Fig 3b: Streaked Dwarf Porcupine (*Coendou ichillus*): extensive bristle quills on the dorsum and flanks.

Figs 4a-c: Long-tailed Porcupine (*Coendou longicaudatus*) – images 20230620-0225 and -0226.

Fig 4a: Long-tailed Porcupine (*Coendou longicaudatus*): full body.

Fig 4b: Long-tailed Porcupine (*Coendou longicaudatus*): tricoloured quills along the spine (and no bristle quills).

Fig 4c: Long-tailed Porcupine (*Coendou longicaudatus*): white-tipped tricoloured quills on the flanks.

3. Acknowledgements

My thanks to Robert S. Voss (American Museum of Natural History) for confirming the identification of these individuals.

4. References

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